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STYLISTIC APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF PIANIST TEACHERS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800199>

Annotation: This article examines the stylistic approach in the practice of pianist teachers. The performing style of outstanding pianists is characterized.

Keywords: style, listening to music, performing culture, interpretation of the work.

The history of the development of the stylistic approach in music pedagogy has existed since the emergence of the very concept of "stylishness". It should be noted the significance of the activities of the outstanding pianist F. Busoni. "For Busoni the interpreter, the unity and integrity of the performing interpretation is undeniably the highest artistic principle. When interpreting the content of a particular work, he often emphasizes the inseparability of the artistic idea, image, expressed feeling and form."¹.

The outstanding Austrian pianist Arthur Schnabel noted that without knowing the composer's work, it is unthinkable to understand his individual work. In his judgments, he called on performers of Beethoven's sonatas to listen to his quartets, and performers of Bach's preludes and fugues to know his vocal works well, thereby penetrating the author's style and understanding the patterns of his work.

The great German teacher K. A. Martinsen in his book "Methods of Individual Piano Teaching" identifies three main styles of piano playing, corresponding to three directions in art: classicism, romanticism and expressionism.

Describing the classical style of piano playing, he notes the meticulous work on the details in the musical text, paying attention to the accuracy of the execution of such elements as rhythm, dynamic shades, finger stroke, which determines the appropriate sound characteristic of the composer's style. K. A. Martinsen calls Hans Bülow the standard of classical style in the history of piano performance.

The outstanding Russian composer and pianist A. Rubinstein, K. A. Martinsen categorizes him as the most prominent representative of the romantic

¹ Мадинковская А.В. Фортепианно – исполнительское интонирование.- М.1990 с 130

style in piano performance. This style of performance is characterized by the transmission of the “poetic idea of the work,” which overcomes the entire work in one breath.

With the work of the outstanding pianist F. Busoni, K. A. Martinsen identifies an expressionist style of performance, which becomes objective through subjectivism.

Each performing style has its own set of technical techniques aimed at creating an artistic image characteristic of the personality of the composer who lived in a certain era.

The creator of the stylistic approach to piano pedagogy in Russia was A. G. Rubinstein. It was he who was one of the first to express the idea that many editions of the musical text of piano works distort the author's intention. He called for reading the text of the original source and thoroughly conveying the main idea of the work as a result of creative comprehension of its content. In his teaching practice, he used the technique of performing Chopin's works with Mozart's accompaniment, as a result of which the student immediately understood the features of the style of both composers at the same time.

The methods of piano pedagogy created by A. G. Rubinstein were developed by outstanding followers of his work. So, G.G. Neuhaus did a lot in his teaching career in terms of developing the personality of the future pianist. He was a supporter of the stylistic approach in piano pedagogy and in his lessons he often analyzed stylistic anticipation in the work of this or that composer, finding in Beethoven's work elements characteristic of his immediate heirs - Schumann, Chopin, Brahms, Wagner. All the pedagogical work of G. G. Neuhaus was aimed at identifying performing means in piano performance in connection with the style and content of the work.

The stylistic approach to piano pedagogy of G. G. Neuhaus was aimed at developing the musical culture of his students, their emotional and intellectual side of personality. He required the study of works of literature, painting, sculpture, while performing works by composers belonging to a particular style, in order to form a correct understanding of the poetic images embedded in a particular piano work. In this way he tried to enrich the performer's musical speech, which required a lot of work to embody an artistic image.

Lev Oborin – student of K.N. Igumnogo, winner of the First International Chopin Piano Competition in Warsaw, was an ardent supporter of stylistic work in the piano class in his teaching work. Calling for the study of the historical facts of the creation of a piano work, Lev Oborin carried out painstaking work to create

a sound ideal that corresponded to the musical image and style of the work. His famous phrase regarding the performance of works by Mozart and Haydn: "Mozart has thinned, melting endings of phrases, but in Haydn (sonata in C major) the sound is interrupted and not ended - as if there was a pause waiting for alertness. Do you see these wedges?"²

Pianist M. S. Voskresensky wrote a lot about the features of Lev Oborin's stylistic approach, noting the composer's excellent playing in lessons when it was necessary to demonstrate the features of the composer's performing style. Lev Oborin did not make literary analogies; he looked for stylistic principles in the musical text, in the methods of sound production, in the emotional interpretation of the image.

The founder of the Central Music School at the Moscow Conservatory, an outstanding pianist and teacher, Alexander Goldenweiser, in his article "On Mozart and the performance of his piano works," wrote that the texture of his compositions is distinguished by transparency, so it must be played with some kind of "reduced" sound. At the same time, Mozart's melody should sound particularly light and melodious, each of its passages is an "independent melodic line." G. G. Neuhaus also called Chopin's passages "accelerated melody." This performance interpretation of piano passages from representatives of different styles is an example of the connection between the styles of these two composers.

The outstanding pianist S. Feinberg paid great attention to the creation of a romantic performing piano style through rhythm in his works. In his book "Pianism as an Art," he notes new forms of rhythmic pattern, corresponding to the romantic pathos of performance characteristic of Chopin, Schubert, and Schumann. He notes the emergence in their work of new methods of interpreting the artistic image, as a result of the introduction of new methods of sound production, pianistic technique, and fingering. Thus, in piano pedagogy, "The student must enter the performing culture of the style to which the given work belongs and follow the stylistic features created by the composer"³

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